

Adding CUDA® Support to Cling:JIT Compile to GPUs

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2020 Virtual LLVM Developers' Meeting

October 6th-8th 2020

Introduction

Using Cling

A terminal window titled "Tilix: Default" showing the execution of the Cling shell. The prompt is "simeon@ELMN3:~\$ cling". The output displays a welcome message: "***** CLING *****", instructions to "Type C++ code and press enter to run it" and "Type .q to exit", and a separator line. The user enters "#include <iostream>" and "std::cout << \"Hello Cling\" << std::endl;". The output is "Hello Cling". The prompt returns to "[cling]\$".

```
simeon@ELMN3:~$ cling

***** CLING *****
* Type C++ code and press enter to run it *
*           Type .q to exit           *
*****

[cling]$ #include <iostream>
[cling]$ std::cout << "Hello Cling" << std::endl;
Hello Cling
[cling]$
```

```
#include "cling/Interpreter/Interpreter.h"

int main(int argc, char *argv){
    auto cling = cling::Interpreter(argc, argv);
    return 0;
}
```


A screenshot of the JupyterLab interface in Mozilla Firefox. The browser address bar shows "localhost:8888/lab". The JupyterLab menu bar includes File, Edit, View, Run, Kernel, Tabs, Settings, and Help. The active notebook is "Basics.ipynb" with a "C++14" kernel. The code cell contains "#include <iostream>" and "std::cout << \"Hello World\" << std::endl;". The output of the cell is "Hello World". The status bar at the bottom shows "0 s. 2 C++14 | Idle", "Mode: Command", "Ln 1, Col 1", and "Basics.ipynb".

Properties

- Read-Eval-Print loop principle
- Does not interpret → the code is JIT compiled
- Fully compatible to existing libraries
 - Can include header files, load unmodified shared libraries and JIT compile C++ source code
- Modifications on syntax and semantic of C++
 - No main() function → everything in global space
 - Missing semicolon at the end of the statement will print the return value
 - Just allowed in the Cling terminal interface or Jupyter Notebook

CPU/GPU Model

CPU

GPU

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GPU

- Why GPU: Better performance for certain algorithms
- Why CUDA: existing algorithms and widest distribution

Basic concept

Extendable application flow

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Transaction 1
(initial state)

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Transaction 2
`int i = 3;`

Extendable application flow

Transaction 1
(initial state)

Transaction 2
`int i = 3;`

Transaction 3
`i = i + 3;`

Creating a single transaction

Input

Metaparser

Parser

AST-Transformer

Code Generator

Executor

Creating a single transaction

Input

foo()

```
***** CLING *****
* Type C++ code and press enter to run it *
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[cling]$ int foo() { return 3;}
[cling]$ foo()
```

Class references:
cling::UserInterface

Creating a single transaction

Input

Metaparser

```
void __cling_Un1Qu32(void* vpClingValue)
{
    foo();
}
```

Tasks of the Metaparser

- Transforms source code
- Detects meta commands
 - e.g.: .L libz.so
 - Linking the shared library z

Class references:

cling::Metaprocessor

cling::utils::getWrapPoint

Creating a single transaction

Input

Metaparser

Parser

Properties of the Parser

- Non-modified Clang parser
- Needs valid C++ code

Class references:

`cling::IncrementalParser`

`clang::Parser`

`clang::ASTConsumer`

Creating a single transaction

Tasks of the AST-Transformer

- Enables functionality
 - e.g. CUDA device kernel inliner
- Adds error protection
 - e.g. nullptr access
- Adds cling specific features
 - Shadow namespaces for redefinition

Class references:

`cling::ASTTransformer`

`llvm::legacy::PassManager`

Creating a single transaction

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AST-Transformer

Code Generator

```
push rbp
mov rbp, rsp
sub rsp, 8
mov QWORD PTR [rbp-8], rdi
call foo()
nop
leave
ret
```

Class references:
cling::IncrementalJIT
llvm::orc

Creating a single transaction

Input

```
foo()  
(int) 3
```

Metaparser

Parser

AST-Transformer

Code Generator

Executor

```
***** CLING *****  
* Type C++ code and press enter to run it *  
*                                     Type .q to exit *  
*****  
[cling]$ int foo() { return 3;}  
[cling]$ foo()  
(int) 3  
[cling]$
```

Class references:
cling::IncrementalExecutor

Challenges

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1) Is interactive CUDA C++ possible?

- The driver API allows it, but we want to use the runtime API
- Answered with many experiments with modified LLVM IR and prototypes

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2) How does Cling understand CUDA C++?

- CUDA C++ is not valid C/C++ → e.g. `foo<<<1,1>>>()`;
- Google's GPUCC project solved the problem for the compiler pipeline → only needed to be activated in Cling
- Metaparser does not use the Clang parser

Sources: Google. *gpucc: An Open-Source GPGPU Compiler*

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3) How to integrate the device pipeline?

- Cling was not designed for a second compiler pipeline
- Solved a lot of different implementation tasks

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 - In general, the documentation is good ...
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 - The LLVM documentation is really good
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 - The LLVM documentation is really good
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 - The Cling documentation is rudimentary and there are no other similar projects
- The CUDA Runtime API was not used interactively until now
 - No experience
 - Some workarounds necessary

Implementation

General Implementation

Versions:
Cling 0.7
Clang/LLVM 5.0

General Implementation

Detail Problem: Metaparser + CUDA

- Problem
 - The Metaparser is completely self-written and parses the “interactive” C++ semantic and the meta commands of Cling
 - The semantic of C++ is complex, the Cling extension makes it even more complex and the CUDA extension too
 - A lot of implementation work is necessary to cover all cases
- Solution
 - Still looking for an optimum solution
 - The most important cases are covered
 - Raw input mode as workaround
- Possible improvements
 - Modifying the Clang parser to handle the “interactive” C++ semantic of Cling

Function references:
cling::utils::getWrapPoint

Detail Problem: Catching errors

- Problem
 - The interpreter runtime and the user code use the same process and memory space. If a segmentation fault occurs in the user code, the entire interpreter crashes.
- Solution
 - Catch the errors with code analysis before the code is executed.
 - Current solution is not generally applicable
 - e.g. Segmentation faults via indirect pointers

Detail Problem: Updating the Clang/LLVM base

- Problems
 - Each new Clang/LLVM version supports new CUDA versions, C++ features and has a lot of bug fixes especially with respect to CUDA.
 - The C++ API is not stable and changes continuously. The JIT backend is also continuously developed further.
 - Cling requires a patched version of Clang/LLVM.
 - Updating the Clang specific patches causes a lot of work.
- Possible Solution
 - RFC for simple Clang REPL by Vassil Vassilev (August 2020)
 - Move as many REPL specific patches as possible upstream to Clang

What is still missing

- Some C++ and CUDA statements, although supported by Clang 5.0 on CUDA 8.0
 - e.g. CUDA `__constant__` memory
 - and CUDA global `__device__` memory
- Not all Cling features work with CUDA yet
 - e.g. redefinition of kernels via namespace shadowing
- Metaparser does not detect all valid CUDA C++ statements
- Error catching needs to be improved

Application Areas

Application areas

- Cling was initially developed for **large data analysis** in HEP physics
- Big, **interactive simulation** with GPUs
- **Teaching** GPU programming
- Easing **development** and debugging

The logo for alpaka, featuring the word "alpaka" in a blue sans-serif font. The letter "p" is stylized as an orange outline of a alpaca's head and neck.

<https://github.com/alpaka-group/alpaka>

<https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu/>

Summary

Summary

- First interactive C++ JIT compiler for the CUDA runtime API
- Added a dual compiler instance concept to Cling, which can be used for other GPU APIs (AMD, Intel)
- Most features already upstream in cling master
- Interactive CUDA C++ in Jupyter Notebook enables new areas of application
 - Data analysis in notebooks with GPUs
 - Big, interactive simulations with GPUs
 - Teaching GPU programming
 - Easing development and debugging

Versions:
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Detail Problem: Clang CUDA expected a completed TU

- Problem
 - How does CUDA register kernels? No official documentation.
 - The Compiler generates the `__cuda_module_ctor` and `__cuda_module_dtor` functions which register and unregister the kernels and register the functions in the global constructor and destructor.
 - Cling creates the functions for each transaction. But Cling is lazy and only translates the first occurrence of `__cuda_module_ctor` into machine code and reuses it for each transaction. So you can only register one kernel in each cling instance.
- Solution
 - Make the function names `__cuda_module_ctor` and `__cuda_module_dtor` unique.

Class references:
UnqiueCUDACTorDtorName

Detail Problem: Embedding the Fatbin Generator

- Problem
 - The LLVM IR code of the device compiler pipeline is translated into Nvidia PTX code (a kind of assembler) and embedded in a fatbinary file (struct with meta data and ptx code).
 - Compared to the PTX code, the fatbin struct is not officially specified. Only Nvidia's external fatbin tool is available for embedding PTX code in the fatbin struct.
- Solution
 - Reimplementation of the fatbin tool based on a header file from the CUDA SDK in "llvm-project-cxxjit"
 - Thanks to Hal Finkel

Class references:
`cling::IncrementalCUDADeviceCompiler`